

Mapping Research Topics on Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking : VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the LDR ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the LDR ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the LDR ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 526 journal publications regarding the LDR ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the LDR ratio are divided into 4 clusters and 177 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 58 topics around the influence of the LDR ratio and 19 topics about the determinants of the LDR ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around LDR ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) has a big influence on banking operational activities. Banks that have a high LDR mean taking greater risks in providing credit. On the other hand, banks that have a low LDR can be considered inefficient in managing existing funds, so that they are less than optimal in maximizing the potential profits that can be obtained. Basically, the higher the LDR, the more funds the bank will lend. However, this is not always a bad thing, depending on economic conditions and the existing banking structure. For example, at certain times, such as in sluggish economic conditions or when there is a need for capital, banks may need to increase LDR to earn income from loan interest and obtain additional capital. On the other hand, an LDR that is too high can also indicate that the bank is too aggressive in providing credit, which can increase the risk of uncontrolled credit and can ultimately affect the stability of the financial system as a whole. Therefore, banks are required to monitor their LDR carefully and try to keep their LDR at a healthy and safe level.

The use of LDR as an indicator of banking health has developed over time. In the 1990s, Bank Indonesia implemented minimum LDR requirements for banks in Indonesia as an effort to limit credit risk and maintain financial system stability. This minimum LDR requirement was raised to 85% in 1998 in response to the Asian financial crisis. However, in 2004, the minimum LDR requirement was removed by Bank Indonesia as part of financial sector reforms. Even though the minimum LDR requirement has been removed, the use of LDR

as an indicator of banking health is still used by regulators and investors. Banks are expected to maintain a healthy LDR, which usually ranges from 70-90%. In addition, with the development of technology, banks are also using risk management systems to monitor their LDR in real-time and carry out more accurate credit risk analysis. This helps banks minimize credit risk and maintain overall financial system stability. Overall, LDR has a very important role in monitoring banking health and maintaining overall financial system stability.

LDR is still the ratio that is more commonly used to measure credit risk in banking. Several studies have been conducted to evaluate the use of LAR as an alternative or complement to LDR. First, one of the studies evaluating LAR was conducted on 129 banks in the European Union and showed that LAR was better at predicting credit risk than LDR. This study also shows that LAR is more sensitive to changes in credit risk than LDR. This shows that LAR can be a more accurate tool in monitoring credit risk in banking. Second, other research conducted shows that LAR can provide more accurate information about credit risk in micro banks. This research was conducted on micro banks in 17 countries and shows that LAR is more reliable than LDR in predicting credit risk in micro banks. Third, several studies also show that the use of LAR can help regulators monitor systemic risk in banking, which shows that LAR can be used as an indicator to monitor systemic risk in European banks. The results of this study show that LAR has a strong relationship with systemic risk and can provide an early signal about the possibility of a financial crisis. Although there is still debate about the effectiveness of LAR in monitoring credit risk and systemic risk in banking, these studies show that LAR has the potential to be a more accurate tool in monitoring credit risk in banking. Therefore, LAR needs to continue to be explored and developed to improve risk management in banking and minimize uncontrolled credit risks.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around LDR in Sharia and Conventional Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding LDR. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research LDR. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding LDR ratios in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) is a ratio that measures how much the bank has lent money compared to the amount of funds available from deposits. In this case, the savings in question are funds placed by customers in the bank in the form of deposits, savings and current accounts. LDR is calculated by dividing the total credit provided by the bank by the total funds placed by customers in the form of savings. For example, if a bank has credit of 800 billion rupiah and deposits of 1 trillion rupiah, then the bank's LDR is 80%. LDR is one of the important indicators used by banking authorities to monitor bank financial health. As a general rule, banks are expected to have a stable and healthy LDR, where the amount of credit provided does not exceed the amount

of deposits received. Banks with high LDR tend to have higher credit risk and can be vulnerable to poor liquidity.

Bibliometric studies are Quantitative research methods are used to analyze scientific works and published literature. This method involves collecting quantitative data from bibliographic sources such as journals, books, and conference articles, and then analyzing this data to evaluate the quality, impact, and influence of the publication. In bibliometric studies, researchers can use various metrics such as citation frequency, journal impact factor, h-index, and so on to evaluate a particular publication, author, or journal. The aim of a bibliometric study is to provide information about research trends, strengths and weaknesses of a research area, as well as assist in decision making and strategic planning. Bibliometric studies are often used in the social sciences and humanities, but can also be applied in various other scientific disciplines. This method can help researchers to understand developments and trends in a research field, and can be a useful tool to assist in planning and developing future research.

VOSviewer is software used for bibliometric analysis and visualization of bibliometric data. VOSviewer is designed to analyze bibliographic data sets such as journal articles, books, and other publications. This software can be used to produce importance maps, network diagrams, and other visual representations of bibliometric data. VOSviewer uses social network analysis and clustering techniques to group and visualize bibliometric data. This software allows users to analyze bibliometric data sets in various formats such as text file format, Microsoft Excel file, or contents file format (isi.cns.nl). In bibliometric analysis, VOSviewer can be used to identify groups of authors or institutions related to a particular topic, to evaluate the interrelationships between research topics, or to find the most frequently cited articles in a research field. VOSviewer is very popular among researchers and professionals in the field of bibliometrics and data analysis, especially in social network analysis. This software has been used in various fields such as social sciences, medical sciences, and engineering sciences to analyze academic publications and evaluate research performance.

Studies Literature review is a type of research carried out by collecting, analyzing and reconstructing information and knowledge contained in literary sources such as books, journal articles and other publications that are relevant to a particular research topic or problem. Literature study A review is usually carried out as an initial stage of research to help researchers understand the history and development of research that has been carried out in that field, as well as to identify gaps in knowledge or research that still needs to be carried out. Literature review studies can be carried out systematically, namely by developing a predetermined protocol or search method, thereby ensuring that all relevant literature sources have been found and evaluated. Literature review studies can also be carried out narratively, that is, by exploring literature sources more freely without following a strict search protocol. The purpose of a literature review study is to provide an overview of existing knowledge in a particular research area and to find gaps in knowledge that still need to be studied further. The results of the literature review study can be used to design hypotheses or conceptual frameworks in further research, as well as to develop recommendations or best practices in the field.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in

literature review studies. The object of the research is the Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on LDR in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords “Loan to Deposit Ratio” and “LDR” throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding LDR using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around LDR using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around LDR using a literature review study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications Regarding Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 526 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2003 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding LDR by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2003	1	2013	20	2019	46
2006	1	2014	28	2020	61
2009	3	2015	36	2021	75
2010	3	2016	43	2022	80
2011	3	2017	57	2023	4
2012	7	2018	58		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Mapping Regarding Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

- Cluster 3, consists of 34 topic items, namely: car influence analysis, analysis technique, autocorrelation test, bank Indonesia, bopo, bpr, classical assumption testing, coefficient, determination test, expense, f test, financial report, heteroscedasticity test, hypothesis testing, level, multicollinearity test, multiple linear regression, multiple regression analysis, net interest margin, nim, normality test, npl bopo, ojk, regression, rural bank, significance level, t test, variable.
- Cluster 4, consists of 15 topic items, namely: assets, Bank Mandiri, Bank Rakyat Indonesia, deposit ratio to return, equity, liquidity, NPL LDR, Persero, PT BRI, ratio to return, return, Roe, state, TBK.

Mapping Literature Review Study regarding the Influence of Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) on Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 58 influences of LDR on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Audit Report Lag. Research shows that LDR has a positive influence on Audit Report Lag in banking. This is because the higher the LDR, the higher the credit risk faced by the bank. High credit risk will increase complexity and caution in auditing bank financial reports, thereby extending the audit report lag. Therefore, there is a need for good credit risk management so that audit report lag can be minimized.

(2) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. Research shows that LDR has a negative influence on CAR in banking. This is because the higher the LDR, the higher the credit risk faced by the bank. If credit risks are not properly anticipated, the bank will need greater capital to cover these risks. Therefore, there is a need for good credit risk management so that CAR can be increased.

(3) Allowance for Impairment Losses. Research shows that LDR has a positive influence on reserves for impairment losses in banks. This is because the higher the LDR, the greater the possibility of problem loans that require reserves for impairment losses. Therefore, banks need to pay attention to the quality of credit provided and adjust the amount of loss reserves to the risks they face.

(4) Debt to Asset Ratio/DAR. Research shows that LDR has a positive influence on DAR in banking. This is because the higher the LDR, the greater the possibility that the bank will need additional funding from the financial market, which can increase the size of bank debt and increase the DAR.

(5) Credit expansion. LDR has a positive influence on credit expansion in banking. The higher the LDR, the greater the amount of funds distributed in the form of loans by the bank. This can expand the credit base and increase bank growth. However, an increase in credit that is not balanced with growth in deposits can increase credit risk and bank liquidity risk.

(6) Earnings Per Share/EPS. LDR can have a positive or negative influence on EPS, depending on the strategy and credit risk management carried out by the bank. If the bank is able to expand its credit base in a healthy manner and manage credit risk well, then LDR can have a positive influence on EPS. On the other hand, if a bank takes credit risk that is not balanced with deposit growth, then LDR can increase credit risk and liquidity risk which can reduce EPS.

(7) Financial Sustainability Ratio. LDR can have a positive or negative influence on the Financial Sustainability Ratio, depending on how the bank manages credit and funding risks. If banks are able to manage credit and

funding risks well, LDR can have a positive influence on the Financial Sustainability Ratio by expanding the credit base and increasing bank growth. However, an increase in credit that is not balanced with growth in deposits can increase credit risk and bank liquidity risk which can reduce the Financial Sustainability Ratio.

(8) Financial Distress. LDR can have a negative influence on financial Distress if the bank is unable to manage credit and funding risks properly. If a bank takes credit risk that is not balanced with deposit growth, the LDR can increase the bank's credit risk and liquidity risk which can cause the bank to experience financial distress. In addition, an LDR that is too high can increase liquidity risk which can worsen the bank's financial condition.

(9) Intermediation function. LDR can have a positive or negative influence on the intermediation function depending on how the bank manages credit and funding risks. If banks are able to manage credit and funding risks well, LDR can have a positive influence on the intermediation function by expanding the credit base and increasing bank growth. However, an increase in credit that is not balanced with growth in deposits can increase credit risk and bank liquidity risk which can reduce the bank's intermediation function.

(10) Share price. LDR can have a positive or negative influence on bank share prices, depending on how the bank manages credit and funding risks. If the bank is able to manage credit and funding risks well, LDR can have a positive influence on the bank's share price by increasing bank growth and bank financial performance. However, an increase in credit that is not balanced with growth in deposits can increase credit risk and bank liquidity risk which can reduce bank share prices.

(11) Indication of window dressing practices for Third Party Funds/DPK. LDR can have an influence on DPK window dressing practices because it can affect bank liquidity ratios. An increase in LDR that is too high can cause an increase in liquidity risk, so banks need to look for alternative funding that is more stable and does not depend on TPF. If a bank only relies on TPF as the main source of funding, the practice of DPK window dressing can occur when the bank takes action to reduce the amount of TPF at the end of the reporting period.

(12) Inflation. LDR can influence inflation by increasing or decreasing the amount of credit disbursed by banks. If banks distribute too much credit with a high LDR, this can increase inflation because it increases the amount of money circulating in society. On the other hand, if banks distribute too little credit with a low LDR, this can reduce inflation because it reduces the amount of money circulating in society.

(13) Amount of credit distribution. LDR can affect the amount of credit disbursement because banks need to consider the balance between credit and funding. An increase in LDR can have a positive influence on the amount of credit disbursement because it can increase the number of funding sources for credit. However, an increase in LDR that is too high can cause an increase in credit risk and liquidity risk, so banks need to consider credit and liquidity risk management in order to maintain credit quality and bank business sustainability.

(14) Deposit amount. LDR can affect the amount of deposits because LDR affects the interest offered by banks on deposit products. The higher the LDR, the higher the interest the bank must pay on third party funds (DPK) such as deposits, because banks need to withdraw funds from customers in order to meet funding needs to distribute credit.

(15) Credit distribution policy. LDR can influence credit distribution policies because LDR can influence the level of credit risk and bank liquidity risk. An increase in LDR can increase liquidity risk and credit risk because banks are more dependent on funding from TPF to distribute credit.

(16) Capital adequacy. LDR can affect capital adequacy because LDR can affect credit risk and bank liquidity risk. An increase in LDR can increase credit risk and bank liquidity risk, so banks need to consider credit and liquidity risk management to ensure bank capital adequacy.

(17) Hedging decisions. A high LDR can reduce a bank's ability to hedge because the bank has made many loans and does not have many funds available to invest in hedging instruments. Conversely, a low LDR can increase a bank's ability to hedge because the bank has more funds available to invest in hedging instruments.

(18) Problem/bad credit. A high LDR can increase the risk of non-performing/bad credit because banks have provided many loans and most likely have fewer funds available to cover emerging credit risks. A low LDR can reduce the risk of non-performing/bad credit because the bank has more funds available to cover emerging credit risks.

(19) Investment credit. A high LDR can limit a bank's ability to provide investment credit because the bank has already provided many loans and may not have sufficient funds available to provide additional credit. Conversely, a low LDR can increase a bank's ability to provide investment credit because the bank has more funds available to provide additional credit.

(20) Working capital credit. A high LDR can limit a bank's ability to provide working capital credit because the bank has already provided many loans and may not have sufficient funds available to provide additional credit. Conversely, a low LDR can increase a bank's ability to provide working capital credit because the bank has more funds available to provide additional credit.

(21) Operating profit. A high LDR can increase a bank's operational profit because the bank has provided many loans and earned higher interest income. However, a high LDR can also increase bank operational costs because banks have to pay higher interest on customer deposits. A low LDR can reduce a bank's operating profit because the bank has less interest income, but the bank's operational costs are also lower because the bank does not have to pay higher interest on customer deposits.

(22) Net profit. The effect of LDR on bank net profit will depend on the relationship between interest income and operational costs. If interest income is higher than operational costs, then a high LDR can increase the bank's net profit. However, if operational costs are higher than interest income, then a low LDR can increase the bank's net profit because the bank's operational costs are lower.

(23) Earnings management. High LDR can cause earnings management in banking. This can happen because banks may tend to increase loan interest rates or reduce deposit interest rates in order to maintain or increase profits. However, if the bank does this, it can affect the bank's reputation and can harm customers. A low LDR, on the other hand, can help banks avoid earnings management practices because banks have more deposit funds available to balance loans and deposits.

(24) Level of IPO Underpricing. LDR can influence the level of IPO underpricing. A high LDR can lead to lower underpricing at the time of an Initial Public Offering (IPO) because banks may have more funds to provide loans to

potential IPO investors. Conversely, a low LDR can lead to higher underpricing because banks may have less funds to provide loans to potential IPO investors.

(25) Net Interest Margin/NIM. LDR can affect NIM. A high LDR can increase NIM because the bank has provided many loans and earned higher interest income. However, a high LDR can also increase interest costs on customer deposits and can reduce NIM. A low LDR can reduce NIM because banks have less interest income from loans, but interest costs on customer deposits are also lower.

(26) Net Profit Margin/NPM. LDR can affect NPM in banking. A high LDR can reduce NPM because banks may have to pay higher interest on loaned funds, thereby increasing bank operational costs. However, a low LDR can increase NPM because banks have more deposit funds available to balance loans and deposits, so that bank operational costs decrease.

(27) Company value. LDR can also affect company value in banking. A high LDR can reduce company value because banks may have difficulty repaying loans if a financial crisis occurs. A low LDR, on the other hand, can increase company value because the bank has more deposit funds available to balance loans and deposits, making it more stable in the face of a financial crisis.

(28) Non Performing Loans/NPL. LDR can affect the NPL level in banking. A high LDR can increase the risk of NPLs because banks may provide too many loans and have insufficient funds to balance their credit portfolio. Conversely, a low LDR can reduce NPL risk because banks have more deposit funds available to balance their credit portfolio.

(29) Going Concern audit opinion. LDR can influence Going's audit opinion Concern about banking. A high LDR can cause a Going audit opinion Negative concern because the bank may experience difficulty in repaying the loan if a financial crisis occurs, thereby calling into question the bank's viability in the future. Conversely, a low LDR can increase audit opinion Going Concern because banks have more deposit funds available to balance loans and deposits, so they are more stable in the face of a financial crisis.

(30) Financing. LDR can affect banking financing. Financing is a source of funding obtained by banks to meet their capital needs. A high LDR can make it difficult for a bank to obtain financing because the bank may be considered to have a higher credit risk. On the other hand, a low LDR can make it easier for banks to obtain financing because banks are considered to have lower credit risk.

(31) Credit offers. LDR can affect credit offers at banks. A high LDR can reduce credit offers because banks may have a lack of funds to balance their credit portfolio. Conversely, a low LDR can increase credit supply because banks have more deposit funds available to balance their credit portfolio.

(32) Income before taxes. LDR can affect income before tax in banking. A low LDR can limit pre-tax income because banks have fewer funds available to provide as loans, which can affect the amount of income generated. On the other hand, a high LDR can increase pre-tax income because banks have more funds available to provide as loans, which can affect the amount of income generated.

(33) Bank interest income. LDR can affect bank interest income in banking. A high LDR can increase a bank's interest income because the bank provides more loans, thereby increasing the amount of interest received. On the other hand, a low LDR can limit the bank's interest income because the bank provides fewer loans, so the amount of interest received decreases.

(34) Credit distribution. LDR can affect credit distribution to banks. A high LDR can affect credit distribution because banks may have to limit the amount of credit provided due to limited availability of funds. Conversely, a low LDR can increase credit distribution because banks have more funds available to provide as credit.

(35) Distribution of People's Business Credit/KUR. LDR can affect KUR distribution to banks. KUR is a government program that provides loans to small and medium businesses at low interest rates. Banks participating in the KUR program must meet certain requirements, including the LDR set by Bank Indonesia. A high LDR can limit KUR distribution because banks may have to limit the amount of credit provided due to limited availability of funds. Conversely, a low LDR can increase KUR distribution because banks have more funds available to provide as loans.

(36) Credit distribution for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises/MSMEs. LDR can affect MSME credit distribution to banks. MSMEs are an important sector in the Indonesian economy and banking is often the main source of financing for MSMEs. A high LDR can limit MSME credit distribution because banks may have to limit the amount of credit provided due to limited availability of funds. On the other hand, a low LDR can increase MSME credit distribution because banks have more funds available to provide as credit.

(37) Distribution of Home Ownership Credit/KPR. LDR can affect KPR distribution to banks. KPR is one type of credit that is most in demand by Indonesian people. A high LDR can limit mortgage distribution because banks may have to limit the amount of credit provided due to limited availability of funds. On the other hand, a low LDR can increase mortgage distribution because banks have more funds available to provide as credit.

(38) Credit growth. LDR can influence credit growth in banks. A high LDR can limit credit growth because banks may have to limit the amount of credit provided due to limited availability of funds. Conversely, a low LDR can increase credit growth because banks have more funds available to provide as credit.

(39) Growth in Small and Medium Enterprise/SME loans. LDR can influence the growth of SME loans to banks. SMEs are an important sector in the Indonesian economy and banking is often the main source of financing for SMEs. A high LDR can limit the growth of SME loans because banks may have to limit the amount of credit provided due to limited funding availability. Conversely, a low LDR can increase SME loan growth because banks have more funds available to provide as credit.

(40) Profit growth. LDR can influence profit growth in banking. A high LDR can increase the risk of bad credit and bank funding costs, which can reduce bank profit growth. Conversely, a low LDR can increase bank profits due to lower credit risk and lower funding costs.

(41) Achievement of profit. LDR can influence the achievement of profits in banking. A high LDR can increase the risk of bad credit and bank funding costs, thereby reducing the bank's profit achievement. Conversely, a low LDR can increase bank profits due to lower credit risk and lower funding costs.

(42) Changes in profit. LDR can influence changes in banking profits. A high LDR can increase the risk of bad credit and bank funding costs, thereby reducing changes in bank profits. Conversely, a low LDR can increase changes in bank profits due to lower credit risk and lower funding costs.

(43) Price Earning Ratio/PER. LDR can affect the Price Earning Ratio (PER) in banking. A high LDR can reduce PER because investors may perceive

that bank credit risk is higher and earnings per share tend to decrease. Conversely, a low LDR can increase PER because investors may assume that bank credit risk is lower and earnings per share tend to increase.

(44) Proportion of operating income. LDR can affect the proportion of operating income in banking. A high LDR can indicate that the bank relies on loans to finance its business operations, thereby affecting the proportion of operating income. On the other hand, a low LDR can indicate that the bank has sufficient deposit funds to finance its business operations, thereby affecting the proportion of operating income.

(45) Prediction of problematic conditions. LDR can also influence predictions of problematic conditions in banking. A high LDR can indicate a higher credit risk, so the bank may have problems repaying the loan. Conversely, a low LDR may indicate lower credit risk, so the bank may be safer and more stable.

(46) Bank ratings. LDR can also affect bank ratings by rating agencies. Rating agencies tend to give higher ratings to banks with low LDR because it shows the bank's ability to manage credit risk well. On the other hand, banks with a high LDR tend to get a lower rating because they are considered riskier.

(47) Liquidity risk. LDR can affect liquidity risk in banking. A high LDR can indicate that a bank is more dependent on loans to finance its operations, thereby increasing liquidity risk when deposits fall. Conversely, a low LDR can indicate that the bank has sufficient deposit funds to finance its operations, thereby minimizing liquidity risk.

(48) Return On Assets/ROA. LDR can also affect Return On Assets (ROA) in banking. ROA shows the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns. A low LDR can increase ROA because the bank has more deposit funds that can be used to generate profits. On the other hand, a high LDR can reduce ROA because the bank has to pay higher interest to attract loans.

(49) Return On Equity/ROE. High LDR can reduce ROE in banking. This happens because when a bank provides more loans than the savings it has, the bank must borrow funds from outside to cover the lack of required funds. The interest costs on these loans can then reduce the bank's net profit and therefore reduce ROE.

(50) Stock returns. LDR can also influence stock returns in banking. A low LDR can increase stock returns because banks have more deposit funds that can be used to generate profits, thereby increasing company value. On the other hand, a high LDR can reduce stock returns because banks have to pay higher interest to withdraw loans, thereby reducing the profits generated.

(51) Profitability. A balanced LDR can increase banking profitability. In the short term, if a bank has a high LDR, it will allow the bank to provide more loans and earn higher interest income. However, in the long term, if LDR continues to increase, high borrowing costs can reduce bank profitability.

(52) Shareholder Value. A balanced LDR can increase shareholder value in banking. In the short term, if a bank has a high LDR, it can provide more loans and earn higher interest income, which can increase the value of shares. However, in the long term, if LDR continues to increase and is not balanced with healthy profit growth, the value of bank shares may fall due to increased risk and high borrowing costs. Therefore, a balanced LDR is important to create long-term value for shareholders.

(53) Spread Based Income. LDR can affect Spread Based Income (SBI) in banking. SBI is the difference between the interest rate charged on credit and the interest rate paid on deposits. Under normal conditions, the higher the LDR,

the more difficult it is for banks to obtain cheap funds, which can affect the bank's SBI.

(54) Bank stability. LDR can also affect bank stability. When the LDR is high, banks tend to be more vulnerable to liquidity risk due to their dependence on funds received from customers. However, if the LDR is too low, banks may have difficulty providing credit and generating income.

(55) Third Party Funds/DPK interest rates. LDR can affect the DPK interest rates offered by banks. When LDR is high, banks tend to offer higher interest rates on deposits to attract more funds from customers. However, if the LDR is too low, banks can offer lower interest rates to reduce the cost of funds and increase profitability.

(56) Term deposit interest rate. The higher the LDR of a bank, the lower the possibility of the bank offering high interest rates to time deposit customers. This happens because the bank has to keep most of the funds received from time deposit customers to meet loan needs. Therefore, if a bank's LDR is high, then the bank may offer lower deposit interest rates to maintain sufficient capital to provide loans.

(57) Total credits. LDR can affect the total credit provided by banks. The higher a bank's LDR, the less funds available to provide loans. Therefore, banks that have a high LDR tend to be more careful in providing loans. In the short term, this can reduce the amount of credit approved by the bank. However, in the long term, banks that keep their LDR stable can provide benefits because they can reduce the risk of credit failure and maintain the bank's financial health.

(58) Total MSME credit. LDR can also have an impact on the total credit provided by banks to micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs). The higher the LDR of a bank, the more difficult it is for the bank to distribute credit to MSMEs because the bank has limited funds to finance MSME credit. Conversely, banks with low LDRs can offer more MSME credit because they have more funds available for loans. Therefore, LDR can affect MSMEs' access to credit and banks' ability to meet credit demand from the MSMEs segment.

Literature Review Studies regarding Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) Determinant Variables in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 19 LDR determinant variables in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) BI rate. The BI rate is a reference interest rate set by Bank Indonesia and is used as a basis for banks in determining credit and savings interest rates. When the BI rate rises, the credit interest rates offered by banks will tend to rise. In this case, LDR will tend to decrease because customers will be reluctant to borrow money at higher interest rates.

(2) Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO. BOPO is the ratio between operational costs and bank operational income. The lower the BOPO ratio, the more efficient the bank's operational costs and the greater the profits earned. In this case, LDR can be positively influenced because banks can provide lower interest rates to customers.

(3) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. CAR is the ratio between bank capital and asset risk. The greater the CAR ratio, the greater the bank's capital to bear the credit risk taken. In this case, LDR can be influenced positively because banks have greater capacity to distribute credit.

(4) Third Party Funds/DPK. DPK is funds received by the bank from third parties, such as customers who save at the bank. The larger the bank's DPK,

the greater the funds available to be distributed as credit. In this case, LDR can be influenced positively because the bank has more funds to distribute as credit.

(5) Minimum Statutory Reserve/GWM. GWM is the minimum amount of funds that must be kept by banks in the form of demand deposits at Bank Indonesia. The amount of GWM that must be saved varies depending on the type of bank and the amount of funds it has. In this case, the GWM can negatively affect the LDR because the bank must hold part of the funds in the form of demand deposits at Bank Indonesia.

(6) Inflation. Inflation is a general increase in the prices of goods and services in the economy. When inflation rises, the value of money will decrease, so customers will need more money to buy the same goods and services. In this case, LDR can be negatively influenced because customers will be more reluctant to borrow money at higher interest rates to offset the increasing cost of living.

(7) Credit distribution policy. Credit distribution policies implemented by banks can significantly influence LDR. If banks tighten credit distribution policies, LDR may decrease because banks will be more selective in providing credit to customers. On the other hand, if the bank relaxes its credit distribution policy, the LDR can increase because the bank will distribute more credit.

(8) Quality of Productive Assets/KAP. Productive Asset Quality (KAP) is the ratio between non-performing loans and total credit owned by the bank. The lower the KAP ratio, the better the credit quality the bank has. In this case, LDR can be positively influenced because banks can provide lower interest rates to customers.

(9) Mergers. A merger is the process of combining two or more banks into one entity. Mergers can affect LDR significantly because the merged bank will have more funds available to distribute as credit. In this case, LDR may increase after the merger.

(10) Currency exchange rates. Currency exchange rates can affect LDR significantly because of their impact on the economy as a whole. If the currency exchange rate depreciates, it will be more difficult for banks to obtain funds from abroad. On the other hand, if the currency exchange rate appreciates, it will be easier for banks to obtain funds from abroad. In this case, the LDR can be negatively affected if the currency exchange rate depreciates.

(11) Non Performing Loans/NPL. Non-Performing Loans (NPL) are loans that are not paid by customers and have passed the payment deadline determined by the bank. The higher the NPL ratio, the greater the risk the bank must bear. In this case, LDR can be negatively influenced because banks will be more careful in disbursing credit if the NPL ratio is higher.

(12) Net Interest Margin/NIM. Net Interest Margin (NIM) is the difference between interest income and interest costs incurred by the bank. The greater the NIM, the greater the profit the bank will gain. In this case, LDR can be influenced positively because banks will distribute more credit to get higher interest income.

(13) Covid-19 Pandemic. The Covid-19 pandemic can affect LDR significantly because of its impact on the economy as a whole. The Covid-19 pandemic can cause a decrease in people's income, which in turn can reduce demand for credit. In this case, LDR can be negatively affected because it will be more difficult for banks to distribute credit.

(14) Economic growth. Economic growth can influence LDR significantly because good economic conditions can increase demand for credit. If economic growth increases, the LDR can increase because banks will distribute more

credit. On the other hand, if economic growth declines, the LDR may decrease because banks will be more careful in distributing credit.

(15) Net Foreign Exchange Position/NOP. Net Foreign Exchange Position (PDN) is the difference between foreign exchange reserves and foreign debt owned by a country. The greater the PDN, the greater a country's ability to pay foreign debt and obtain funding from abroad. In this case, LDR can be positively influenced if PDN becomes larger, because it will be easier for banks to obtain funds from abroad.

(16) Return On Assets/ROA. ROA is a ratio that measures the efficiency of using bank assets in generating profits. The higher the ROA, the better the bank's performance in utilizing assets to generate profits. ROA can influence LDR positively, because banks that have high ROA tend to have higher trust from investors, making it easier to obtain funds from investors.

(17) Return On Equity/ROE. ROE is a ratio that measures the efficiency of using a bank's own capital in generating profits. The higher the ROE, the better the bank's performance in utilizing its own capital to generate profits. ROE can also influence LDR positively, because banks that have high ROE tend to have higher trust from investors, making it easier to obtain funds from investors.

(18) Interest rates. Interest rates are an important factor that influences LDR in banking. An increase in interest rates can make it more difficult for banks to distribute credit, so that the LDR can decrease. On the other hand, a decrease in interest rates can make it easier for banks to distribute credit, so that LDR can increase.

(19) Bank size. Bank size can influence LDR because larger banks tend to have more sources of funds and more opportunities to channel credit. So larger banks tend to have a higher LDR compared to smaller banks.

Conclusions and Recommendations

the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2003 to 2023 which came from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 526 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the LDR ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 4 clusters and 177 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 75 topics, cluster 2 consists of 53 topics, cluster 3 consists of 34 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 15 topics. Third, based on mapping studies literature review, there are 58 topics related to the influence of the LDR ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Audit Report Lag, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Allowance for Impairment Losses, Debt to Asset Ratio/DAR, credit expansion, Earning Per Share/EPS, Financial Sustainability Ratio, Financial Distress, intermediation function, share prices, Indication of window dressing practices of Third Party Funds/DPK, inflation, amount of credit disbursement, amount of deposits, credit disbursement policy, capital adequacy, hedging decisions, problem/bad credit, investment credit, working capital credit, operating profit, net profit, earnings management, level of IPO Underpricing, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Net Profit Margin/NPM, company value, Non Performing Loans/NPL, going concern audit opinion, financing, credit offering, income before tax, bank interest income, credit distribution, People's Business Credit/KUR distribution, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise/MSME credit distribution, Home Ownership Credit/KPR distribution, credit growth,

Small and Medium Enterprise/UKM loan growth, profit growth, profit achievement, changes in profit, Price Earning Ratio/PER, proportion of operating income, prediction of problematic conditions, bank rating, liquidity risk, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, and stock returns, profitability, shareholder value, spread based income, bank stability, Third Party Funds/DPK interest rates, term deposit interest rates, total credit, and total MSME credit.

Furthermore, there are 19 topics related to the determinants of the LDR ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: BI rate, Operational Costs to Operating Income/BOPO, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Third Party Funds/DPK, Minimum Statutory Reserve/GWM, inflation, credit distribution policy, Quality of Productive Assets/KAP, mergers, currency exchange rates, Non Performing Loans/NPL, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Covid-19 pandemic, economic growth, Net Open Position/GDP, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, interest rates, and bank size.

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